

THE ROLE OF CULTURE IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

Baxronova Martaba Sobirovna

*English teacher for lawyers, Department
of General Education Sciences*

Abstract. Culture is considered a central concept in anthropology, encompassing the range of phenomena that are transmitted through social learning in human societies. This article describes about the role of the culture in teaching foreign languages.

Keywords: culture, culture in language, cultural elements, system of values.

Culture is an umbrella term which encompasses the social behavior, institutions, and norms found in human societies, as well as the knowledge, beliefs, arts, laws, customs, capabilities, and habits of the individuals in these groups. Culture is often originated from or attributed to a specific region or location. Humans acquire culture through the learning processes of enculturation and socialization, which is shown by the diversity of cultures across societies. A cultural norm codifies acceptable conduct in society; it serves as a guideline for behavior, dress, language, and demeanor in a situation, which serves as a template for expectations in a social group. Accepting only a monoculture in a social group can bear risks, just as a single species can wither in the face of environmental change, for lack of functional responses to the change. Thus in military culture, valor is counted a typical behavior for an individual and duty, honor, and loyalty to the social group are counted as virtues or functional responses in the continuum of conflict. In the practice of religion, analogous attributes can be identified in a social group. Cultural change, or repositioning, is the reconstruction of a cultural concept of a society. Cultures are internally affected by both forces encouraging change and forces resisting change. Cultures are externally affected via contact between societies. Culture should be regarded as the set of distinctive spiritual, material, intellectual and emotional features of society or a social group,

and encompasses, in addition to art and literature, lifestyles, ways of living together, value systems, traditions and beliefs. Culture shapes individual's worldviews and the way communities address the changes and challenges of their societies. For this reason, education serves as a critical vehicle for transmitting these value systems as well as for learning from the humanity's diversity of worldviews, and for inspiring future creativity and innovation. Culture and education are two inseparable parameters and they are interdependent. Any educational pattern gets its guidance from the cultural patterns of a society. For instance, in a society with a spiritual pattern of culture, the educational focus would be on the achievement of moral and eternal values of life. On the contrary, if the culture of a society is materialistic, then its educational pattern will be shaped for the attainment of materialistic values and comforts. A society which does not follow any culture definitely has no definite educational organization. So, the culture of a country has a very powerful impact on its educational system. Today while human lives continue to live in local realities, the lives and experiences of youth growing up will be allied to, social processes, economic realities, technological and media innovations, and cultural flows that go across international borders with ever greater momentum. These worldwide transformations will involve youth to adapt to new skills that are well ahead of what most educational systems can now distribute.

Culture plays a vital role in every individual's life. It brings together numerous elements to create a unique way of living for different people. Some of the major elements that exist in every culture and many change with time as the society progresses are symbols, language, values, and religion. The first element is variety of symbols. A symbol is used to stand for something. People who share a same culture attach a specific denotation to an object, gesture, sound, or image. For instance, Christians use a cross as a significant symbol to the religion. It is not just two pieces of wood attached to each other, nor is it just an old object of torture and execution. To Christians, it represents the basis of their whole religion, and they have great respect for the symbol. The second factor in every culture is a

language. Language is a structure of words and symbols used to communicate with other community. Beside English, Spanish, French there are other unique languages which belong to certain groups of people. Those are slang, common phrases and body language. For example, English is most common and fluent spoken language in America and Britain, however, we see and hear slangs and phrases that mean different things; American cookies are British biscuits; American French fries are British chips, and so on.

A system of value is a culture which is defined for standard what is good or pleasant. There is a share system of values which is used by member of the cultures to evaluate what is right and what is wrong. In West, people are individualistic, they strongly believe in competition and emphasize on individual achievement. According to the culture whoever gets promotion is appreciated for his/her hard work and talent. However, in East the collectivist values of culture are in oppose to the West. In East there is a strong believe on welcoming the collaboration and an individual's achievement is only as good as his/her contribution to the group.

References:

1. Ralph L. Holloway Jr. (1969). "Culture: A Human domain". *Current Anthropology*. 10 (4): 395–412.
2. Haviland, William A.; McBride, Bunny; Prins, Harald E.L.; Walrath, Dana (2011). *Cultural Anthropology: The Human Challenge*. Wadsworth/Cengage Learning.
3. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF CLIPPINGS IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC CONFERENCE" INNOVATIVE TRENDS IN SCIENCE, PRACTICE AND EDUCATION". – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 2. – C. 145-149.
4. Abdullayev A. A. THE ROLE OF TRANSLATION IN TEACHING FL //International Academic Research Journal Impact Factor 7.4. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 80-83.

5. Obidjonovna M. F. SOME TEACHING PRINCIPLES OF READING IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE //Archive of Conferences. – 2021. – Т. 23. – №. 1. – С. 18-20.
6. Ismailov A. R. STYLISTIC AND PRAGMATIC ASPECT IN DISCOURSE ANALYSIS //Wschodnioeuropejskie Czasopismo Naukowe. – 2018. – №. 4-4. – С. 62-65.
7. Ismailov A. R. THE PROBLEM OF THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL CULTURE IN MODERN METHODICS OF TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES //Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире. – 2021. – №. 4-8. – С. 46-49.
8. Исмаилов А. Вопрос формирования педагогической культуры в современной методике преподавания иностранных языков //Иностранная филология: язык, литература, образование. – 2021. – №. 2 (79). – С. 49-56.
9. Rustamovich D. I. A. et al. The role of verbal and non-verbal communication in learning foreign language //World Bulletin of Social Sciences. – 2022. – Т. 9. – С. 10-11.
10. Farruxovna B. G. Linguistic Methods in Sentence Analysis //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. – 2022. – Т. 13. – С. 54-56.
11. Болтакулова Г. Ф. Синтаксическая дистрибуция компонентов, выражающих темпоральность в английском и узбекском языках //Вестник Челябинского государственного университета. – 2016. – №. 9 (391). – С. 44-50.
12. Болтакулова Г. Ф. Способы выражения обстоятельства времени в английском и русском языках и его место в предложении //Молодой ученый. – 2015. – №. 14. – С. 583-585.